

MONTE CARLO SITUATION MONITORING TECHNIQUES TO QUANTIFY PURCHASES OF MAIN RAW MATERIALS IN FOOD PRODUCTION

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Abstract

An application of Monte Carlo simulation techniques model to find the quantity of purchasing main raw materials suitable for animal feed production. The objective is to find the appropriate order quantity of main raw materials in animal feed production. There are 3 types of raw materials studied: wheat bran, cassava mill, and barley. The number of options for the new raw material purchasing policy is 27. The least amount of raw material ordering is Policy 1, which will purchase 2,050 kilograms of wheat bran, 1,550 kilograms of cassava mill, and 800 kilograms of barley. The largest order of raw materials is Policy 27: Purchase 3,650 kilograms of wheat bran, 3,450 kilograms of cassava mill and 1,480 kilograms of barley. Appropriate raw material order quantity That makes the total cost of inventory management for all 3 types of raw materials the lowest, consisting of order quantities of wheat bran, cassava mill, and barley equal to 2,050, 1,550, and 800 kilograms per time, respectively, and the point of ordering wheat, cassava mill and the appropriate amount of barley is 3,560, 3,270, 1,342 kilograms, respectively.

Keywords: Simulation, Monte Carlo, Wheat Bran, Cassava Mill, Barley.

1. INTRODUCTION

The animal feed industry as a midstream industry is very important because it connects agricultural crop cultivation with economic animal husbandry to provide a source of protein for the population. Whenever there is a problem in the animal feed industry (midstream industry of the food chain), such as insufficient agricultural raw materials to meet demand, shortage of agricultural raw materials during certain seasons, higher agricultural raw material prices, and substandard agricultural raw materials, etc., it will lead to production problems in downstream industries in the food chain, such as expensive, low-quality, unsafe animal products and products, and insufficient consumption.

The animal feed industry of Thailand has continuously developed in many areas, such as research, academics, substitution of imported animal feed raw materials, calculation of animal feed formulas, improvement of animal feed production processes, and improvement of packaging and transportation, etc. The current animal feed industry is also related to other production and service sectors, such as industrial crop production, economic animal production, processed food industry, transportation business, and communication business.

Therefore, the animal feed industry is very important to the country's macro and micro economy, generating a large amount of income for those involved. In 2017, the estimated

value throughout the animal production industry chain, such as animal feed factories, livestock and aquaculture farms, and processed food business, animal and aquatic products for domestic consumption and export, up to 315,000, 630,000 and 875,000 million baht, respectively (exchange rate 1 US\$ = 35 baht) (Jittima Kantanamanlakul, 2019)

Case Study Company started its operation in 2004 under the name Eastern International Trading Co., Ltd. by importing cat litter for distribution as the first company in Thailand under the brand name “Kitty Love” and it was very well received by cat owners. Therefore, the company’s own brand “Kat-To” was created. In 2007, the company developed and expanded its business to pet food products, starting with cat food under the brand name “Mac’s Cat”. With a good response from consumers, in 2009 the Case Study Company started producing dog food under the brands “Pan Pan” and “Mac’s Dog”. In 2017, it established a modern pet food factory under the name NEKtech PETFOOD Co., Ltd... Case Study Company started producing premium pet food by using Krill, which is a highly beneficial ingredient in terms of nutritional value, as the main ingredient in pet food under the brand name “N&K Premium Food (NEKtech PETFOOD CO., LTD., 2023)

The study found that the appropriate amount of raw material orders for animal feed production is still out of production due to the limitations of raw materials that must be stored. The duration of raw material quality from the overall study of operations from January to October 2023, it was found that the company had to face the problem of higher demand than expected. There was a shortage of goods, causing the company to lose sales opportunities frequently. Due to many reasons, such as insufficient orders to meet the demand from the actual amount of raw material use that fluctuates and is higher than expected Inventory management (Nattawut Thongmee, 2020) Raw material transportation takes a long time and is delayed, making it impossible to deliver on time The amount of raw materials in the system does not match the actual amount that can be counted, causing errors In planning to order raw materials The company must solve problems in order to receive raw materials for production in time for delivery to customers on time (Chaiwat Kittidecha, Chitrakarn Panyawong, Natchaya Khampuenkam & Ekarat Rattanadilok Na Phuket, 2022) In addition, there was a problem that the amount of raw materials was still more than necessary from the actual demand less than the forecast.

This results in insufficient warehouse space for storage in some seasons. Managing inventory levels to be at an appropriate level (Anchalee Saejiam, Kanchanapa Amaratchakul & Sivika Dusadeenod, 2019). Therefore, it is very important for the company in both cases of raw material shortages and raw material surpluses. The researcher therefore chose to analyze and improve the purchase order quantity along with finding a new purchase point sufficient to meet the demand, which will enable the appropriate inventory level. The objective of this research is to find the appropriate purchase quantity of the main raw materials for animal feed production by applying the Monte Carlo simulation technique (Thai Physics Association, 2021). (Suwanna Phonpakdee & Nipas Leenatham, 2020). (Kanoksak Srijan & Udomsap Poolsawasdi, 2018).

2. METHODOLOGY

1. Basic information

The main raw materials are wheat bran, crushed cassava, and barley. The raw materials are sourced from the province where the factory is located and has a production capacity of 2,080 tons per year. The details of the main raw materials are as follows:

Table 1: shows details of the main raw materials

Main raw materials	Demand (kg)	Percentage
Wheat bran	904,000	43.48
Cassava pulp	810,000	38.96
Barley	365,000	17.56
Total	2,079,000	100

2. Raw material ordering process

The raw material ordering process consists of selecting raw materials that have been produced in 3 months and have standards for use as animal feed. Raw material storage will be in the form of packing in sacks, 50 kilograms per sack, and then placed on pallets, 50 sacks per pallet, and using raw materials by withdrawing one pallet at a time, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Raw material ordering process

3. Research Instruments

The research instruments are as follows:

- 1) Monte Carlo technique
- 2) Mathematical equations for simulation

4. Data Collection

- 1) Put the data of the main raw materials into the table of Monte Carlo technique
- 2) Analyze the data of the main raw materials to find the appropriate value

3. RESULTS

1. Raw material demand data collection

This raw material demand data collection collected data on the demand volume of all 3 types of raw materials in August 2023 for 31 days.

Table 2: Data on the demand for wheat bran raw materials

Demand (kg)	Occurrence frequency (times)
0-2,000	5
2001-2,500	4
2501-3,000	5
3,001-3,500	7
3,501-4,000	10

Table 3: Data on the demand for ground cassava

Demand (kg)	Occurrence frequency (times)
0-1,500	3
1,501-2,000	5
2,001-2,500	5
2,501-3,000	10
3,001-3,500	8

Table 4: Barley raw material demand data

Demand (kg)	Occurrence frequency (times)
0-500	6
501-1,000	12
1,001-1,500	13

The minimum and maximum wheat raw material requirements are 2,000 kg and 4,000 kg, as shown in Table 2. The minimum and maximum cassava raw material requirements are 1,500 kg and 3,500 kg, as shown in Table 3. The minimum and maximum barley raw material requirements are 500 kg and 1,500 kg, as shown in Table 4.

2. Determination of random number event conditions

In creating a Monte Carlo simulation model to find the appropriate order quantity and order point, the conditions of the random numbers obtained from the demand data in August must be determined. This research must create the conditions of the random numbers of all 3 types of raw materials to represent the demand event. The data that will occur is the frequency of demand in various quantities, arranged from highest to lowest, to consider how many times each quantity occurs, and then find the probability of demand in various quantities that are likely to occur. Find the cumulative percentage of the previously found probability to use in simulating the demand situation of each type of raw material.

Table 5: Construction of random variable conditions of wheat bran demand.

Wheat bran demand	number of times	probability	cumulative probability
0	5	0.161	0.161
2,050	1	0.032	0.194
2,200	1	0.032	0.226
2,250	1	0.032	0.258
2,340	1	0.032	0.290
2,500	3	0.097	0.387

2,800	2	0.065	0.452
3,050	3	0.097	0.548
3,150	1	0.032	0.581
3,400	3	0.097	0.677
3,500	9	0.290	0.968
3,650	1	0.032	1.000
Total	31	1	

Table 6: Construction of random variable conditions of demand for cassava pulp.

Wheat bran demand	number of times	probability	cumulative probability
0	3	0.097	0.097
1,550	2	0.065	0.161
1,800	2	0.065	0.226
1,950	1	0.032	0.258
2,200	2	0.065	0.323
2,450	3	0.097	0.419
2,550	4	0.129	0.548
2,700	3	0.097	0.645
2,950	3	0.097	0.742
3,050	4	0.129	0.871
3,150	3	0.097	0.968
3,450	1	0.032	1.000
Total	31	1	

Table 7: Construction of the random variable conditions of barley demand.

Wheat bran demand	number of times	probability	cumulative probability
0	6	0.194	0.194
800	6	0.194	0.387
980	6	0.194	0.581
1,100	7	0.226	0.806
1,250	5	0.161	0.968
1,480	1	0.032	1.000
Total	31	1	

The demand for wheat bran starts at 0 kg with a probability of 0.161. The demand for wheat bran is 2,050 kg with a probability of 0.032. The cumulative probability is 0.194. The cumulative probability is 1.00, which represents the demand for wheat bran of 3,650 kg, as shown in Table 5.

The demand for ground cassava starts at 0 kg with a probability of 0.097. The demand for cassava is 1,550 kg with a probability of 0.065. The cumulative probability is 0.161. The cumulative probability is 1.00, which represents the demand for cassava of 3,450 kg, as shown in Table 6.

The demand for barley starts at 0 kg with a probability of 0.194. The demand for barley is 800 kg with a probability of 0.194. The cumulative probability is 0.387. The cumulative probability is 1.00, which represents the demand for barley of 1,480 kg, as shown in Table 7.

3. Find a new order pattern and find a new order point (ROP)

From the data collected from the raw material demand in August 2023, it can be seen that the amount of use of each type of raw material has an uncertain daily demand. In this research, the data on the demand for all 3 types of raw materials has a non-normal distribution pattern. Therefore, the appropriate order point can be found by using the theory of Lordahl and Bookbinder (Lordahl, A. E. and Bookbinder, J. H. 1994) to find the new order point.

The calculation method is as follows:

If $(n + 1) P \geq n$, then $ROP = x_y$ (demand data in the y th order)

If $(n + 1) p < n$, then $ROP = (1-\omega)x_y + \omega x_{y+1}$ Where ROP represents the level of reordering

Where n is the number of data (raw material demand data during the production period $n = 31$)

P is the confidence value (Set to 95%: $P=0.95$) Substitute n and p into the equation as follows:

$$(n+1) P = (31+1) \times 0.95 = 30.4$$

$$y + \omega < n, \text{ we get } y = 30, \omega = 0.4$$

Arrange the wheat bran demand data, sorting the raw material usage from least to most.

Table 8: shows the ranking of wheat bran demand from least to most.

0	0	0	0	0	2,050	2,200
2,250	2,340	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,800	2,800
3,050	3,050	3,050	3,150	3,400	3,400	3,400
3,500	3,500	3,500	3,500	3,500	3,500	3,500
3,500	3,500	3,650				

Table 9: shows the order of demand from least to most for cassava pulp.

0	0	0	1,550	1,550	1,800	1,800
1,950	2,200	2,200	2,450	2,450	2,450	2,550
2,550	2,550	2,550	2,700	2,700	2,700	2,950
2,950	2,950	3,050	3,050	3,050	3,050	3,150
3,150	3,150	3,450				

Table 10: shows the order of demand from least to most for barley.

0	0	0	0	0	0	800
800	800	800	800	800	980	980
980	980	980	980	1,100	1,100	1,100
1,100	1,100	1,100	1,100	1,250	1,250	1,250
1,250	1,250	1,480				

The demand for wheat bran in August 2023 from low to high, starting from 2,050 kilograms to a demand of 3,650 kilograms, as shown in Table 8. The demand for ground cassava

in August 2023 from low to high, starting from 1,550 kilograms to a demand of 3,450 kilograms, as shown in Table 9. The demand for barley in August 2023 from low to high, starting from 800 kilograms to a demand of 1,480 kilograms, as shown in Table 10.

Table 11: New orders considered

raw material	New order quantity specified (kg)			
	Min	Average	Max	ROP
Wheat bran	2,050	2,430	3,650	3,560
Cassava pulp	1,550	2,170	3,450	3,270
Barley	800	980	1,480	1,342

New raw material order quantities: Wheat bran will have Min = 2,050 kg Average = 2,430 kg Max = 3,650 kg and ROP = 3,560 kg; Cassava flour will have Min = 1,550 kg Average = 2,170 kg Max = 3m450 kg and ROP = 3,270 kg; Barley will have Min = 800 kg Average = 980 kg Max = 1,480 kg and ROP = 1,342 kg as shown in Table 11. There are 27 alternative raw material purchasing policies in total, with the least raw material purchasing policy being Policy 1, which will purchase 2,050 kilograms of wheat bran, 1,550 kilograms of ground cassava, and 800 kilograms of barley. The most raw material purchasing policy is Policy 27, which will purchase 3,650 kilograms of wheat bran, 3,450 kilograms of ground cassava, and 1,480 kilograms of barley, as shown in Table 12.

Table 12: Number of new ordering policy alternatives

Policy that	Order quantity (kg)		
	Wheat bran	Cassava pulp	Barley
	ROP = 3,560	ROP = 3,270	ROP = 1,342
1	2,050	1,550	800
2	2,050	1,550	980
3	2,050	1,550	1,480
4	2,050	2,170	800
5	2,050	2,170	980
6	2,050	2,170	1,480
7	2,050	3,450	800
8	2,050	3,450	980
9	2,050	3,450	1,480
10	2,430	1,550	800
11	2,430	1,550	980
12	2,430	1,550	1,480
13	2,430	2,170	800
14	2,430	2,170	980
15	2,430	2,170	1,480
16	2,430	3,450	800
17	2,430	3,450	980
18	2,430	3,450	1,480
19	3,650	1,550	800
20	3,650	1,550	980
21	3,650	1,550	1,480
22	3,650	2,170	800
23	3,650	2,170	980
24	3,650	2,170	1,480
25	3,650	3,450	800
26	3,650	3,450	980
27	3,650	3,450	1,480

4. CONCLUSION

1. Results of raw material demand

The results of the data on the amount of demand for 3 types of raw materials, namely wheat bran, crushed cassava, and barley, in August 2023 for 31 days are summarized as follows:

The lowest demand for wheat raw materials is 2,000 kilograms and the highest is 4,000 kilograms, followed by the lowest demand for crushed cassava raw materials at 1,500 kilograms and the highest is 3,500 kilograms, and the lowest demand for barley raw materials is 500 kilograms and the highest is 1,500 kilograms, respectively.

2. Results of setting the event conditions of random numbers

The demand for wheat bran starts at 0 kg with a probability of 0.161. The demand for wheat bran is 2,050 kg with a probability of 0.032. The cumulative probability is 0.194. The cumulative probability is 1.00, which represents the demand for wheat bran of 3,650 kg.

The demand for cassava pulp starts at 0 kg with a probability of 0.097. The demand for cassava pulp is 1,550 kg with a probability of 0.065. The cumulative probability is 0.161. The cumulative probability is 1.00, which represents the demand for cassava of 3,450 kg.

The demand for barley starts at 0 kg with a probability of 0.194. The demand for barley is 800 kg with a probability of 0.194. The cumulative probability is 0.387. The cumulative probability is 1.00, which represents the demand for barley of 1,480 kg.

3. Find a new order pattern and find a new order point. (ROP)

New raw material purchase order quantity: Wheat bran will have Min = 2,050 kg, Average = 2,430 kg, Max = 3,650 kg, and ROP = 3,560 kg; Cassava pulp will have Min = 1,550 kg, Average = 2,170 kg, Max = 3,450 kg, and ROP = 3,270 kg; Barley will have Min = 800 kg, Average = 980 kg, Max = 1,480 kg, and ROP = 1,342 kg.

There are 27 new raw material purchase policy options. The least raw material purchase is Policy 1, which will purchase 2,050 kg of wheat bran, 1,550 kg of cassava pulp, and 800 kg of barley. The most raw material purchase is Policy 27, which will purchase 3,650 kg of wheat bran, 3,450 kg of cassava pulp, and 1,480 kg of barley.

5. DISCUSSION

The application of Monte Carlo simulation technique to find the appropriate order quantity of the main raw materials for the production of 3 types of animal feed: wheat bran, ground cassava, and barley. The results are discussed as follows:

The results of the simulation to find the appropriate order quantity of the main raw materials for the production of the 3 types of animal feed applied in the research show the appropriate order pattern that can help order the main raw materials, which is consistent with the research (Cherada Khumthanom, 2021). It was found that the appropriate order quantity of the main raw materials in the case study of the steel bar and

steel bar manufacturing company found the appropriate order quantity of the main raw materials in the country of the case study company. And to compare the cost of ordering the main raw materials before and after analyzing the appropriate order quantity of the main raw materials of the case study company the researcher ranked the importance of the raw materials by using the value of the company's order total. It can reduce the total cost of inventory management and reduce the order frequency by 23 times per year, which is 16.78 percent.

Appropriate order quantity of raw materials that makes the total cost of inventory management of the 3 types of raw materials the lowest, consisting of the order quantity of wheat bran, crushed cassava, and barley equal to 2,050, 1,550, and 800 kilograms per time, respectively. And the appropriate ordering point of wheat, crushed cassava, and barley is equal to 3,560, 3,270, and 1,342 kilograms, respectively, which is consistent with the research (Wanlop Phupha, 2014). It was found that the procurement of raw materials in a processed food factory this research aims to find the appropriate ordering policy of raw materials used in a processed food factory such as sausages. Apply Monte Carlo simulation techniques to find the appropriate ordering policy and ordering point by selecting the raw materials with the highest demand for consideration in the research. From the data studied using the ABC principle, it was found that 3 types of raw materials in Group A can be classified: chicken frame, chicken meat, and tapioca flour. Then, data on the historical demand for each type of raw material were collected to create a probability distribution table of demand data to determine the demand for raw materials in stock. To determine the purchasing policy and the ordering point of the 3 types of raw materials, there are 27 policies in total. The simulation is to find the purchasing policy that results in the lowest total cost of inventory management. It was found that the appropriate ordering quantity and the appropriate ordering point that results in the lowest total cost of inventory management of the 3 types of raw materials consist of the ordering quantity of chicken frame, chicken meat and tapioca flour equal to 4,400, 1,000 and 930 kilograms per time, respectively. The appropriate ordering points of chicken frame, chicken meat and tapioca flour are equal to 5,904, 1,416 and 2,760 kilograms, respectively. In addition, it was found that the new purchasing policy results in the lowest inventory management cost, amounting to 20,010,855 baht.

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